

Scenario A
ATP-scale low-noise regime
 $T = 0.0534$
Signal contrast: $C \approx 0.03$
(more distinguishable)

Scenario B
High-noise reference regime
 $T = 0.10$
Signal contrast: $C \approx 0.00$
(low distinguishability)

